

ISic3284

I.Sicily inscription 3284

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

marble

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Alex Antoniou,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Catina

Place of origin (modern)

Catania

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Catania, Museo Civico di

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. [---]A[---]A

2. [---] κ(αὶ) Κυριακή

Apparatus

Korhonen 2004

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 645552

PHI 316262

Bibliography

Korhonen, K. 2004. Le iscrizioni del Museo civico di Catania : storia delle collezioni, cultura epigrafica, edizione. Helsinki. At 180

Libertini, G 1931. Miscellanea epigrafica. *Archivio Storico per la Sicilia Orientale*.

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Libertini (1981) 113 no.4
Ferrua, A 1989. Note e giunte alle iscrizioni cristiane antiche della Sicilia.
Vatican. At no.420

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